

SZ-HB-III-02-01 Search for other students to prepare for exams (English)

Author	@Ricarda Peil ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Alexander Schröter ; @Sönke Erdmann ; @Julia Lehmler ; @Julia Victoria Dinier (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091519
ID	SZ-HB-III-02-01
Title	Search for other students to prepare for exams
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Nadine - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
Short description	Nadine is looking for other students (group) for exam preparation.
Result	knowledge sharing
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario• Process "Help with exam preparation"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nadine is registered at BIRD• Nadine is logged in to BIRD
Components	#buddyfinder #chat
Services / tools	#studoco

Problem scenario

Introduction

In the subject "Advanced Linear Algebra," Nadine has to solve a complex math problem that involves various matrix multiplication techniques. She knows that this question will soon be asked in one of the upcoming exams and wants to make sure that she is able to solve it correctly. Unfortunately, she quickly realizes that she can't solve it.

Problem definition

Nadine wants to understand the problem, not just get the solution. If the question is going to appear on a future exam, she also needs to be able to correctly explain the calculation method. She cannot solve the task on her own.

Background and context

Nadine is studying mathematics for her bachelor's degree. When it comes to the various tasks in her studies, it is not enough for her to just find the right solution; she also wants to understand the process behind it. Her goal isn't to get the best grades at the end of the seminar, but to understand everything in detail so that she can potentially teach it to others later on.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

The fact that Nadine cannot solve the task right away makes her increasingly insecure. She's afraid that this exact problem might be asked in one of her next exams, and she's desperate to have it explained in detail and understand it so she can solve it herself.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Nadine isn't able to solve the problem on her own, and an internet search didn't yield any results. Although she identified the problem and its corresponding solution, the calculation method was not explained, prompting her to continue her search.

Activity scenario

Process "Help with exam preparation"

Step 1: Upon first reading through the problem for the "Advanced Linear Algebra" seminar, Nadine feels unsure. She recognizes that while she has mastered some of the required techniques, she would like to discuss different approaches to gain a more comprehensive understanding.

Step 2: Nadine remembers the BuddyFinder in BIRD. It was recommended by her university as a tool for forming study groups. She opens her laptop and navigates to BIRD.

Step 3: Nadine logs into her verified BIRD account. She then navigates to the BuddyFinder and creates a BuddyFinder profile.

Step 4: Nadine agrees to share her data with the BuddyFinder.

Step 5: Nadine enters the following information into the BuddyFinder search to refine her search:

- subject area: Mathematics, Linear Algebra
- Semester: 5th semester
- Difficulty: Advanced
- Course reference: "Advanced Linear Algebra, Winter semester 2023/24"
- Language: German

Step 6: The BuddyFinder displays several profiles of students with similar interests and needs. Nadine selects the profile of a group of students who are also in their 5th semester of mathematics and attending the same seminar. She would like to join a team because she enjoys working together to learn about different perspectives and possible solutions.

Step 7: Nadine clicks on the group's profile and uses the "Contact" function of the BuddyFinder. She writes a short message describing her concern and expressing her interest in a joint study meeting.

Step 8: The group accepts her contact request via the BuddyFinder and responds within a few hours.

Step 9: In the group chat, Nadine suggests a meeting in the afternoon at the Potsdam University Library to work on the problem together. The attendees bring their notes and the sample solution. They discuss different approaches, compare their solutions, and benefit from each other's knowledge.